

Intercropping – An effective tool to combat pests and pathogens in cotton

Banka Kanda Kishore Reddy¹, SN Malleswari Sadhineni² and V. Chinna Babu Naik³

^{1,2}Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Reddipalle, ANGRAU

³ICAR- Central Institute for Cotton Research, Nagpur

Introduction

Pests and pathogens are a common problem for the cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L) industry, despite the importance of this crop worldwide. Chemical pesticides are currently used for the management of cotton pests and pathogens. While chemical pesticides are generally effective, their continued use can lead to insect resistance, a decrease in natural predators and parasites, a weakening of ecological balance, and environmental degradation. The use of cultural methods, such as intercropping, to reduce pests and pathogens in cotton crops is gaining popularity as a result of rising environmental consciousness and the necessity for cotton grown without compromising on sustainability. Intercropping changes, the ecological structure and environment of the fields, which increases the number of natural enemies and decreases the number of pests and diseases that affect cotton. Intercropping with cotton is an efficient method for minimizing land use conflicts between cotton and other profitable crops like grain.

Appropriate crop combination for intercropping, including growing pest-killing or pest-repelling crops to attract natural enemies. Increased total cotton productivity without a drop in quality is possible through intercropping with cotton-based crops. Cotton that is intercropped with other crops like corn, mungbean, wheat, sorghum and sunflower can either directly attract natural enemies or create habitats for the reproduction of those natural enemies. Natural enemies were more numerous and aphid populations were lower due to the cotton-fennel intercropping. The extra-floral nectaries of sunflowers are a vital resource for helpful arthropods like predators and parasitoids, providing them with water and dissolved sugars. Green lacewings can be protected and their populations increased by planting bait crops of maize, mung beans, or sunflowers surrounding a cotton field (Bastola et al. 2016). Rapeseed develops quickly in the cotton-rape intercropping system, producing luxuriant foliage, although aphids appear abruptly. Rapeseed can

serve as a food and nutrient supplement for natural enemies, such as ladybeetles, aphid parasitoids, and other beneficial insects. To prevent aphid damage to the cotton seedling, they might be released into the fields at an early stage of cotton growth. Cotton-mungbean intercropping drastically alters the microclimate in comparison to a cotton monoculture because mungbeans grow faster and have a greater plant size than cotton in the early season. The intercropped mungbeans and the altered microclimate help natural enemies thrive, drawing in and breeding with predatory ladybeetles. Cotton-barley intercropping can reduce the number of pests like *A. gossypii* and *Helicoverpa armigera* by making more spiders, aphid parasitoids, syrphid flies, minute pirate bugs, predaceous ladybeetles, and green lacewings.

Using trap- or repellent-type crops to capture or repel pests.

Cotton can be protected against pests by being intercropped with other crops, known as trap-crops, such as corn, alfalfa, mung beans, and cowpeas. Both the cotton bollworm and the corn borer prefer maize plants to cotton plants as egg laying hosts in the cotton-maize intercropping system. The number of eggs laid on cotton plants is reduced, as is the resulting harm to the crop. Cotton-cowpea intercropped fields had lower aphid populations because cowpeas served as a food source for predatory ladybeetles.

Microclimatic shifts and insect population losses

Altering the microclimate of cotton fields through intercropping is the third effective method of insect management. The structure of the vegetation, air flow, humidity, and temperature in an intercropping environment are all different from those in a monoculture. Changes in temperature, humidity, wind speed, and light are significantly affected by crops with different plant heights from cotton, such as maize or fruit trees. Population fluctuations caused by cotton pests are strongly related to the impact that climate has on their growth and survival. The health of the crop, the number of natural predators, and the temperature all have a role in determining how well cotton pests thrive. Aphid populations in a cotton-waxy corn intercropped system behaved similarly to those in a monocropped system in both space and time. During the peak seasonal incidence of aphids, the quantity of aphids in the intercropping field was significantly lower than that in the monoculture cotton field.

Acting as natural refuges and delaying the development of Bt cotton pest resistance

A large number of cotton bollworm adults that have not been subjected to the selective pressure of the Bt protein can be produced by creating an untreated refuge. Matings between two

Bt-resistant adults are less likely when susceptible individuals are present. A common tactic in the United States for delaying cotton bollworm resistance to transgenic insect-resistant cotton is to plant a 4% non-Bt cotton refuge without using any pesticides, or plant 20-30% non-Bt cotton around fields of Bt-resistant cotton that can be treated with chemical pesticides to get rid of other pests in the refuge. Models similar to Australia are to be introduced in India as

1. 10% of the total land area was planted with non-Bt cotton that could be consumed by the cotton bollworm.
2. 50% of Bt cotton fields must have non-Bt cotton treated with pesticides other than Bt.
3. 20% of Bt cotton fields should be planted with sorghum or maize without pesticides to control bollworm.

Intercropping reduces the transmission and multiplication of diseases.

Cotton disease incidence and severity can be decreased by intercropping with cereals, as the former can compete with the latter for soil nutrients. Intercropping with wheat, cabbage, watermelon, and sweet melon has helped decrease cotton boll rot. The growth of diseases is typically stymied by the root exudates of plants that are grown in between the main crops. The growth of cotton disease pathogens can be slowed, either directly or indirectly, by fluids from garlic roots (Xiaodan et al. 2014). Garlic was found to dramatically lower the incidence of cotton Fusarium wilt and verticillium wilt in cotton fields that were intercropped with garlic, compared to pure cotton. As a result, root exudates are a crucial tool for preventing the spread of diseases among intercropped plants.

Summary

Efficient intercropping can help control cotton pests and diseases by conserving or attracting natural enemies, trapping or repelling pests, altering the field's microclimate to affect the development of both natural predators and pests and pathogens. The emergence of resistance to Bt cotton by its intended pests can be slowed by the presence of natural refuges provided by these areas. Also, root secretions help prevent cotton infections from developing and spreading. More study of the mechanisms and risk assessments is needed to determine which intercropping strategies produce the best results. The efficiency of intercropping in managing of cotton diseases and pests can be improved with the use of a holistic and strategic programme that incorporates intercropping with agrochemicals.

References

- Xiaodan, Z. H. A. N. G., Jingjing, L. I. A. O., & Weiping, D. E. N. G. (2014). Correlation analysis of the sensitivity of *Fusarium* spp. to garlic root exudates and their pathogenicity to garlic bulb. *Plant Protection*, 40(6), 53-58.
- Bastola, A., Parajulee, M. N., Porter, R. P., Shrestha, R. B., Chen, F. J., & Carroll, S. C. (2016). Intercrop movement of convergent lady beetle, *Hippodamia convergens* (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), between adjacent cotton and alfalfa. *Insect science*, 23(1), 145-156.